

ON-HARMONY 2.0: A comprehensive travelling-heads resource for multi-modal neuroimaging harmonisation

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Introduction: In studies that involve multiple MRI scanners, an important challenge that arises is the dependence of measured imaging features on scanner- and site- dependent factors that are not related to the scanned subject [1-3]. To tackle this problem, several approaches are possible; some of them involve attempting to harmonise as much as possible the acquisition protocols and the processing pipelines [4,5], including using vendor-agnostic sequences [6]; while others directly address the final parameters to try and regress out the non-biological differences [7,8]. In order to assess the nature of these confounding factors for neuroimaging studies, we ran a travelling heads study involving a group of healthy participants, scanned over different 3T MRI systems of several types and vendors across different sites. The Oxford-Nottingham Harmonisation (ON-HARMONY 2) study builds upon our previous work [9] and comprises one of the most comprehensive travelling heads resources with data from 20 subjects (9 subjects with multiple within-scanner repeats), each scanned in 6 3T scanners (Siemens, Philips and GE) and 5 modalities (T1w-MPRAGE, T2w-FLAIR, diffusion MRI, resting-state fMRI, SWI).

Methods: The study ran in two phases (10 subjects per phase) (Figure 1). The first phase took 2 years to complete (median time difference (TD) between first and last rescan for a subject across scanners: 374 days), as interrupted by the COVID19 pandemic. The second phase was completed in less than 6

Figure 1. Summary of the acquisition paradigm for subjects, scanners and modalities involved in each phase of the study (w: wide-bore, n: narrow-bore, ch: Number of head coil channels).

months (TD: 126 days). Phase A involved 3 Siemens, 2 Philips and 1 GE scanner, while Phase B had 2 scanners from each vendor (Figure 1). A better sex balance was maintained in Phase B (50% females vs 20% females in phase A). Acquisition protocols were aligned with the UK Biobank imaging study [10], however adjustments were made to respect best practices for each scanner/imaging site (therefore parameters were not simply nominally matched) [9]. Each participant was scanned in 6 different scanners, while 9 participants (4 in phase A, 5 in B) had in addition 6 within-scanner repeats (most of scanners had at least one participant with 6 within-scanner repeats). That way between-scanner and within-scanner variability for subjects could be characterised and compared to between-subject (i.e. biological) variability, which is typically the variance of interest. All data underwent quality control using MRIQC [11] and eddyQC [12] leading to image-quality metrics (IQMs) for 4 modalities. They were subsequently processed with a modified version [9] of the UK Biobank pipeline [13]. Hundreds of imaging-derived phenotypes (IDPs), i.e. multi-modal imaging features were derived for each session. That way, different pools of IDP and IQM variability could be compared.

Results and Discussion: Figure 2 demonstrates examples of the raw data, depicting a subset of the sessions acquired for each of the participants, across scanners (columns) and modalities (rows). We subsequently extracted IQMs to assess consistency of data quality across subjects and scanners for each imaging modality (Figure 3). In the top plots, each quality metric for each subject was z-scored across the six scanners. The z-scores were then averaged across the subjects. In the bottom plots, each IQM was z-scored across the ten subjects and then averaged across the scanners. The plots indicate that across both phases A and B there are no scanners/subjects that act as major outliers in terms of

image quality. Subsequently, we assessed how the similarity of IDPs changes across different pools of variability (Figure 4). We represented each scan session in terms of the multi-modal imaging features we could extract and computed Spearman correlations across sessions for different IDP groups (subcortical volumes, brain tissue volumes, subcortical T2*, cortical parcel

Figure 2. Example of a subset of the acquired data for a single subject. Five different modalities (three shown here) and 6 scanners, located in five different imaging sites were obtained for all 20 participants. Data from Phase B scanners are shown.

volumes, dMRI regional and tract-wise microstructure (FA, MD, MO, L1, L2, L3), rfMRI functional connectivity node amplitude and edges). Figure 4 shows the median correlation across IDP groups for session pairs belonging to three different pools (between-subject/same scanner, between-scanner/same subject and same-scanner/same-subject). It shows how biological variability (red) has hardly any overlap with scan-rescan variability of a subject (blue) as expected, however it overlaps quite substantially with between-scanner variability (green).

Conclusion: We have presented one of the most comprehensive harmonization resources for multi-modal neuroimaging, which we will use as a testbed to develop and explore both explicit and implicit harmonisation approaches [9].

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Figure 3. IQMs of each session, averaged across each IDP group, then z-scored across subjects and averaged across scanners (upper row) or vice-versa (lower row) for each study phase.

Similarity of session-wise IDPs

Figure 4. Spearman correlation of session IDPs (calculated as the median across groups of the Spearman correlation of IDPs in the same group for each session). Violin plots show IDP similarities across the different categories.

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